

PEDAGOGICAL PSYCHOLOGY AND PSYCHOLOGICAL ACTIVITY IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *In this article, we are talking about educational psychology taken from the developed areas of modern times, which is a key role in this place, since this is the nature of the human spirit and the student. Educational psychology is a network of psychology, a fan of education and training of effective affected factors, laws and mechanisms.*

Keywords: *pedagogical psychology, psychological activity, psychological processes, complex integral.*

All educational institutions in the country should learn the specific psychological laws, its mechanisms, as well as the active, independent, and creative thinking methods of modern knowledge. In this regard, educational psychology is taken from the developed areas of modern times, which is a key role in this place, since this is the nature of the human spirit and the student. Educational psychology is a network of psychology, a fan of education and training of effective affected factors, laws and mechanisms. Educational psychology and psychological activity in educational institutions is a place for two sciences, that is, psychology and pedagogical sciences.

The subject of educational psychology is to study the laws, skills and competencies in educational institutions, the individual differences that occur in these processes, active, independent and creative thinking. He also studies changes in psychological psychology - the impact of education and the psychological performance of students, the psychological performance of students, and the psychological requirements for textbook order. Currently, one of the important tasks of educational psychology is the development of a psychological basis for further improvement of the educational process in an educational institution, which is associated with the transition to this type of new education. At the same time, educational psychology studies the impact of the learning process of student students and studies the psychological foundations of students' self-discipline. The organizer of the educational process of "pedagogical psychology" will also study the teacher, his pedagogical activity. In this case, the achievements of the teacher in the field of education and the psychological processes of his knowledge, skills and abilities are revealed.

In the past, our ancestors did not study in some scientific areas, but the manuscripts of these scientists are of great importance for the manifestations of this knowledge. In particular, Abu Nasr Farabi says that a person is a complex integral and mutually dependent parts in the positive resolution of physiology and the physiological problems associated with it. The knowledge of science factor in the knowledge of science, it is present in birth, but the human body, brain, spirituality, spirit, intellectual knowledge, characteristics, religion, customs, information environment, others in relation to people and similarities, Man will shoot them by their activities, reaches them. His minds, his minds, claim that there will be moral growth spiritual growth. Abu Nasr Farabi: "The teacher must know the psychological characteristics of the student, the teacher

must be able to fully and clearly express his thoughts." Only then will he have a high degree of humanity and reach the pinnacle of happiness.”

Abu Rayhon Beruni, Tasks and positions, thoughts about human development, the development of the young generation is really designed at the core of humanity. The principles of knowledge and education can be observed in all the works of the thinker. It emphasizes man as part of nature. Beruni penetrates deeply into the essence of the educational process and reads education based on taking into account the young characteristics of children. In pedagogical work, man and his happiness were the main problem of education and perfection. Wisdom, and the unity of medicine, the structure of the human body, their nerves and circumstances are still an important foundation of medicine.

According to Abu Ali ibn Sina, the teacher must be persistent, honest, who knows the rules of morality. The teacher must learn the entire inner and outer world and enter into the segments of his mind.

One of the main unique problems is the upbringing of the ideal person Yusuf Khos Khozhib. He is the most perfect in his works, according to how the society imagined. A person who can meet the requirements of society, in accordance with the principles. “Knowledge that will lead to happiness” (“Kutadgu bilig”) is a spiritual source of spiritual and courage, combined, instructions, guidelines, guidelines.

Abdurakhman Jomiy, "Spring Garden" 1487, "The Book of Wisdom of Iskandar" (1486-1487), "Tuhfat-ul-akhror", and other works are described in knowledge of human positive qualities. In the course of education and the teacher in the process of education and teaching, Nasriddin Tusiy is the most important factor: "A teacher is the knowledge of debate", in order to prove the righteousness of one's thoughts and speech, this must be logically expressed ... Teaching speech is never rude or heavy. The inability of the teacher during the lesson can break the case ..."

Mir Alisher Navai "Confusion of the Righteous" 1483 ("Mahbub-ul-Kulub") has moral, friendly relations, talent and abilities. It is emphasized that these psychological criteria are important for the solution of social justice. At the same time, the student evaluates the teacher, even if the student receives the kingdom, and he sees him as a teacher as a central person in the process of education and training. In addition, the role of parents, women, the humility of people in Navai is a harmonious person. Each epic "Hamsa", a creative fantasy, a complex inner experience of a person skillfully illuminated, can also emphasize that the views of the great oriental behavior, teacher and role in society, ethical life, behavior and interpersonal relationships are free and compact in their works.

REFERENCES

1. Nasiba Kholboevna Elmurzaeva. PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION CLUSTER AS A SCIENCE. European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol. 10 No. 3, 2022 ISSN 2056-5852
2. Nasiba Kh. Elmurzayeva. Development Of The Pedagogical (Educational) Cluster. In The Regional Educational Space Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results | Volume 13 | Special Issue 7 | 2022
3. Nasiba Kh. Elmurzayeva. Formation Of A Cluster System. In The Sphere Of Education In Uzbekistan: Problems And Prospects. Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results | Volume 13 | Special Issue 7 | 2022.

4. Nasiba Kh. Elmurzayeva. Formation Of Pedagogical Clusters Of Scientific And Methodical Cooperation Educational Organizations Of Regions (In The Example Of The World Countries). *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results* | Volume 13 | Special Issue 7 | 2022
5. Khimmataliyev, D. O., Abdijalilova, S. A., Elmurzaeva, N. K., Turaev, M. F., Allayorova, S. B., & Janbayeva, M. S. (2022). Formation Of A Cluster System In The Sphere Of Education In Uzbekistan: Problems And Prospects. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results*, 5634-5638.
6. Oblakulovna, Ernazarova Gulnora. "Application Of The Acmeological Approach To Improve The Efficiency Of The Professional Educational Process." *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results* (2023): 2551-2555.
7. Mukhamedov, G. I., Usarov, J. E., Khimmataliev, D. O., Khodjamkulov, U. N., Ernazarova, G. O., & Rasulov, A. N. (2023). Pedagogical Training the Pedagogical and Psychological Foundations of the Innovation Cluster. *Telematique*, 22(01), 29-31.
8. Rakhmanova, M., and M. Meylieva. "Socio-Psychological Features of the Formation of a System of Attitudes to Career Choice in Adolescents." *Indiana Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences* 2.12 (2021): 4-7.
9. Musurmanova, A., Ismailova, Z., Fayzullaev, R., Rakhmonova, M., & Sharifbaeva, H. (2022). Echnologies For The Development Of Technical Competence Of Students On The Basis Of Innovative And Integrated Approaches. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6(3), 1631-1637.
10. Mirzaahmadovna M. S. Learning objectives of dual higher education study //Horizon: Journal of Humanity and Artificial Intelligence. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 4. – C. 192-195.
11. Omonovich K. D., Mirzaahmadovna M. S. The Relevance of the Dual Learning Model for Our Country //Telematique. – 2023. – T. 22. – №. 01. – C. 265–274-265–274.
12. Djanbaeva, M. S., & Allayorova, S. B. (2021). Amaliyotchi psixolog shaxs va mutaxassis sifatida. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(Special Issue 1), 390-394.
13. Qorayev, S. B., & Allayorova, S. B. (2021). Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini pirls xalqaro baholash dasturi tizimiga tayyorlash jarayonini takomillashtirish masalalari. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(2), 443-448.
14. Musurmonov, R., Eshmanova, N., Satbarov, A., & Elmurzaeva, N. (2021). Innovative Activity In Education-The Requirement Of The Period. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*, 8(02), 2021.
15. Barakaevich, Qoraev Samaridin, and Sotbarov Atabek Asilbek Ogli. "Requirements for Preparing Vocational Education Teachers in the Innovation Cluster of Higher Education." *JournalNX*: 952-955.
16. Khimmataliev, D. O., Elmurzayeva, N. K., Sharakhmatova, A. K., Sotbarov, A. A., Khalmatova, D. A., & Jamoldinova, S. N. (2022). Development Of The Pedagogical (Educational) Cluster In The Regional Educational Space. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results*, 5629-5633.
17. Alimjanovna, Khalmatova Dilobad. "The role and significance of volunteers in the process of formation of ecological culture." *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal* 12.4 (2022): 108-111.
18. Khalmatova, D. A. (2021). Formation of ecological culture in students in the process of extracurricular activities on the example of grades (9-11). In *Актуальные Вопросы Современной Науки И Образования* (pp. 201-203).